

THE BEHAVIOR OF THE MALE CONSUMER IN RELATION TO COSMETICS

Brenda Rodrigues Soares - Faculdade de Tecnologia da Zona Leste

brenda.rodrigues@live.com

Abstract

The objective of this article is to understand and analyze the behavior of male consumers in relation to the variety of existing cosmetics in relation to the buying process; and whether the male consumer has become demanding and independent when purchasing cosmetic products. For the analysis of the subject a bibliographic survey was carried out, followed by a quantitative survey, with 8 questions using the Likert scale, with 155 male consumers. The modern man is a demanding and conceited consumer, seeking the cosmetic industry either by professional or personal necessity, worrying about his well-being. In Brazil, the man is becoming more and more vain, with that improving his self-esteem. Abandoning thus, the image of not the concern with appearance.

Keywords: Consumer Behavior; Male Consumer; Cosmetics; Metrosexual.

1. Introduction

Consumption originates in the most remote times of mankind. As markets become increasingly global, it will be important for marketers to manage and understand the cultural issues of consumer behavior in local and international markets (ZIELINSKI and ROBERTSON, 1982).

Their own future economic situation, imagined by consumers, is an important factor in their attitudes towards spending and saving and causes some influence on their current behavior (SARABIA-SANCHEZ, 2005).

The Brazilian Industry of Personal Hygiene, Perfumery and Cosmetics presented an average deflated growth compounded close to 11.4% a.a. In the last 20 years, from an Ex-Factory sales net of sales tax, from R \$ 4.9 billion in 1996 to R \$ 42.6 billion in 2015 (ABIHPEC, 2016).

The global market for personal care products is expected to increase between 3.5% and 4.5% over the next five years, with a total market value of \$ 500 billion by 2020 (KPMG, 2016).

The last CENSUS made in Brazil indicates that, out of a total population of 190 million, 93.4 million are men, or approximately 49% of the total Brazilian population (IBGE, 2010).

In the hygiene and beauty market for men, and especially in cosmetics, the supply has long been ignored by the cosmetics brand. In fact, by the late 1990's, beauty products for men were virtually nonexistent in the market. There was no store space, and men strictly used products in a utilitarian aspect (BLANCHIN; CHAREYRON; LEVERT, 2007).

The problem of this article is what the behavior of the male consumer in relation to cosmetics?

The overall objective is to understand and analyze male consumer behavior with cosmetics.

When examining the consumption of cosmetics, it can not be ignored that it has traditionally been developed for female consumers, since hygiene products are considered as a penetrating element of the consumption of women. However, the changes

occurred in the cosmetics market as men became key consumers for various cosmetics companies (SOUIDEN and DIAGNE, 2009).

Being physically attractive means having better opportunities to find a preferred partner, it is related to the theory that our body and physical appearance play increasingly important roles in contemporary society (LAKSONO and PURWANEGARA, 2014).

With this new preoccupation with appearance emerged the figure of the new man and led to the emergence of the term metrosexual. Resulting from the junction of the words "metropolis" and "heterosexual", the word metrosexual should be understood as the latest concept to define the masculine, urban young consumer who venerates vanity. Despite the sum of the terms, one should not confuse and understand that there is a direct connotation with sex (GARCIA, 2011).

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1 Consumer behavior

According to Kotler and Keller (2006, p.4). The goal of marketing is to know and understand the customer so well that the product or service is appropriate for him and sells himself. Ideally, marketing should result in a customer willing to buy. The only thing needed then would be to make the product or service available.

According to Churchill Jr and Peter (2000, p.4) "Marketing is the process of planning and executing the design, pricing, promotion and distribution of ideas, products and services in order to create exchanges that meet individual and organizational goals."

The marketing mix is the tactical and controllable marketing tool set the company combines to produce the response it wants in the target market. It consists of everything the company can do to influence the demand for its products. The various possibilities can be grouped into four groups of variables known as the 4Ps: products, price, square and promotion (KOTLER and ARMSTRONG, 2007, p.42).

For Solomon (2002, 32), consumer behavior is understood as "the study of the processes involved when individuals or groups select, buy, use, have products or services, ideas or expectations to satisfy needs and desires."

According to Richers (1984), the behavior of the consumer is characterized by the mental and emotional activities performed in the selection, purchase, and use of products and services for the satisfaction of needs and desires.

According to Blackwell, Miniard and Engel (2005) consumer behavior is defined as activities that people engage in when they obtain, consume and dispose of products and services.

Simply speaking, consumer behavior is traditionally thought of as the "why people buy" study, under the premise that it is easier to develop strategies to influence consumers after we understand why people buy certain products or brands. In this way, there are several activities included in the definition of consumer behavior obtaining, consumption and elimination. It is understood that the consumer purchasing decision process is highly influenced by variables internal and external to it, such process is changeable and inconsistent.

2.2 Men's Cosmetics

Cosmetic products have stood out in the market not only in Brazil but also in the world. This is due to the more active and constant participation of consumers of these products, who started to use them more frequently (THEODORIDIS et al, 2013). Personal care expenditure includes elements of shared consumption, for example in the Shared teeth, body lotion, hair care and face care. It follows that the domestic composition as a whole required creates boundary conditions for individual choices (LAKSONO and PURWANEGARA, 2014).

The purchase of hygiene goods, when involved in the procurement process of these products men are more likely to remain loyal to A specific brand, building a strong relationship with it, when it provides them with a mirror to reflect desirable male self-image (YE and ROBERTSON, 2012).

The consumption of beauty products is associated with the desire to promote increased physical attractiveness and (FONTES; BORELLI and CASOTTI, 2012). It is important to consider the world of cosmetics in two distinct parts, the market for men and women. Even if there are no great distinctions between products, these two markets are quite different. In fact, men do not have the same demand for the product. This is why the offer may not be the same for both. The ideal product for most men should have some properties and qualities like being invisible, fast, pleasant to put on, easy to use, no smells and with an efficient result. Men are not looking for a female product,

otherwise, they will continue to use their wife or mother's (BLANCHIN; CHAREYRON; LEVERT, 2007).

Following this trend, several cosmetics corporations have shifted their focus to male consumers, In order to increase their market share. In addition, companies are no longer choosing to produce stereotypes male hygiene products, such as shaving foam and razor blades, but are now increasingly focusing on the development of new products. Major cosmetics companies have created products dedicated to men, such as face creams, anti-wrinkle creams, tanning products, hair coloring and toning gels. Analyzing consumer behavior will help to understand more about the psychological and sociological factors that influence the customer. When buying cosmetics, the male customer decision-making process is influenced by multiple situational factors such as the store environment, the type of distribution, the place of purchase and the sellers (WEBER and VILLEBONNE, 2002).

3. Methodology

Lakatos and Markoni (2010, p.106), the bibliographic research "covers all bibliographies already made public in relation to the subject of study" (newspaper, books, monographs, journals and theses) and other publicly available means to contribute to the Research.

In a complementary way, Cervo, Bervian and Da Silva (2007, p.63) says that exploratory research "does not require the elaboration of hypotheses to be tested at work, being restricted to defining objectives and seeking more information about a particular subject of study. Such studies aim to familiarize themselves with the phenomenon or to obtain a new perception of it and to discover new ideas".

For Richardson (1999) the quantitative research is characterized by the use of quantification, both in the modalities of collecting information and in the treatment of them by means of statistical techniques.

According to Moreira (2002, p.17) in the quantitative research "data collection will emphasize numbers (or information convertible into numbers) that allow to verify the occurrence or not of the consequences, and then the acceptance (although provisional) or not of the hypotheses".

4. Results

A quantitative research was carried out. Applied a questionnaire in Google Docs with 8 alternative questions, published on the social network Facebook. It was applied to male users in which 155 answers were obtained, which allowed to identify and analyze the behavior of male consumers in relation to cosmetics.

According to the results obtained, we can see below in the graph the civil status of the sample.

Figure 1: Marital status

Figure 2: Who buys cosmetics in Single civil status

Figure 3: Who buys cosmetics in Married civil status

In Figures 2, 3 and 4 we can see that most men are buying their own cosmetics, be it single, married or divorced. It is understood that the male consumer, shows himself more interested in the acquisition of cosmetics making himself the choice of his product for consumption.

When asked the male consumer about the quality of the product was influenced at the time of choice, 96.12% say that quality is important, ie we can notice that the

consumer cares about the item that is being consumed and does not search for an item Any for consumption, having a greater concern when choosing.

With the man buying his own cosmetic he tends to research on brands, value, quality and origin.

Based on the questions asked, 83.87% claim to have their favorite brands, 85.16% do not buy the cheapest product, 78.06% claim that national brands are not the best. Of the respondents, 47.2% usually buy their cosmetics in regular stores.

Note that the male consumer is attentive to what is placed in the market, thus doing price and quality research.

The man is a demanding and vain consumer, seeking the cosmetic industry either by professional or personal necessity. The male audience also cares about their well-being.

5. Final considerations

The characteristics that served as the standard for masculinity are changing.

The male consumer is concerned about the appearance, either by the professional or personal.

It is important that companies observe the behavior of this consumer, because for him in the first place is important the quality of the product, therefore, is more demanding.

The man in Brazil is becoming more and more vain, abandoning that image of not worrying about appearance. In addition, the man tends to become more faithful to the brand when it meets his need.

Regarding the problematic of the article was evident independent of the marital status, detected by the research the male consumer is attentive to the new products and that realize the purchase of cosmetics on their own, evidencing a new independent consumer, with own opinion regarding the products, and A change in the status of "male" man, who only bought deodorant, to the "New man" is the term in which is used to refer to metrosexual.

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